

Properties analysis of composite materials for the manufacture of space mirror

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ABSTRACT

This work puts forward requirements of carbon fiber composite for space mirror, and compares properties of common intermediate modulus and high modulus carbon fibers and common resins of composites. Results show that carbon fiber composite for manufacturing space mirror should select high modulus carbon fiber and high toughness resin matrix. High toughness cyanate ester resin C705 and domestic high modulus carbon fiber were selected for manufacturing the prototype space mirror.

Keywords: carbon fiber; composite; space mirror; cyanate ester; resin matrix

INTRODUCTION

Space mirrors were fabricated using continuous carbon fiber reinforced polymer composite (CFRP) materials, which was the development trend of lightweight space optical system. CFRP composite mirrors had been deeply studied for several decades overseas, and many research results had been achieved. Engineering application of high precision composite mirrors was illustrated. PLANCK, RICH, NPOI and ULTRA projects were their typical representatives [1]-[4].

Fig.1 Comparison of specific stiffness and thermal stability of manufacturing materials used for mirror

Space mirror should have these characteristics: ultra lightweight, thermal performance matching, good structural rigidity. Fig.1 shows specific stiffness and thermal stability of manufacturing materials used for mirror. Compared with Zerodur, SiC and other materials used for mirror, carbon fiber composite, such as

HM CFRP, has better comprehensive properties. Excellent characteristics of carbon fiber composite make it a new ideal material for the lightweight reflectors, especially for large diameter and high resolution space mirrors.

While in the replication process, different manufacturing materials would bring different process performances, and the composite mirrors after curing have different in-plane stiffness, which will affect the surface precision of carbon fiber composite mirrors. Therefore, the selection of fiber, resin and prepreg should meet high precision manufacture of CFRP composite space mirror, which is the focus of this paper.

MATERIALS OF CFRP COMPOSITE FOR MIRROR

CFRP composite used in space mirror should meet specific requirements in the fiber、resin and prepreg [5], as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Select requirements of CFRP composite for mirror

	Requirement	Solution
Carbon fiber	High specific stiffness	Choose high modulus or ultrahigh modulus carbon fibers with modulus higher than 250GPa, and with low density
	Good thermal stability	Choose carbon fibers with high coefficient of thermal conduction meanwhile maintain low (close to zero) coefficient of thermal expansion
	Reliable source	Source carbon fibers from reliable suppliers with no export embargo
Resin	Lightweight and high toughness	Select low density and high toughness thermosetting resin with good anti-microcracking ability
	Low moisture absorption and low curing shrinkage	Resin moisture absorption rate be within 2.5% and curing shrinkage rate between 1% and 3%
	Suitable for hot-melt prepreg fabrication	Choose resin with good film-forming ability, good flow property, superior interface bond with carbon fibers and good reproducibility
Prepreg	Good processability	Choose prepreg with good tack and handleability
	Reproducible performances	Confirm prepreg reproducibility from different batches to ensure stable physical properties

Carbon fiber used in the manufacturing of space mirror should be high modulus, low density, and low absolute value of thermal expansion coefficient. High-performance carbon fibers produced by Japan and USA are selected as reinforcement of composite space mirror, and a small amount of carbon fiber produced in other countries with considerable properties are used in manufacturing composite space mirror. Properties of common intermediate modulus and high modulus carbon fiber are shown in Table 2[6] [7].

Polymer matrix functions are not just as a support and protection of carbon fiber reinforcement, but also to transfer load to carbon fibers in the form of shear stress. Common resins including unsaturated polyester, epoxy and phenolics resin, are used in fields with general demands. While high performance resins, such as cyanate ester, bismaleimide and polyimide, are used in fields of special requirements. These resins have different operational performances and processabilities. The properties of the resins for resin matrix composites are shown in Table 3[8] [9].

Table 2 Properties of common intermediate modulus and high modulus carbon fiber abroad

Grade	Type of tow	Density (g/cm ³)	Tensile strength (GPa)	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Breaking elongation(%)	Fiber diameter (μm)	Coefficient of thermal expansion (10 ⁻⁶ /K)	Coefficient of heat conduction (W/m K)	Manufacturer
T800H	6/12	1.81	5.59	294	1.9	5.1	0.0	20	Toray (Japan)
M40J	3/6/12	1.75	4.40	377	1.2	5.0	0.0	38	
M46J	6/12	1.84	4.20	436	1.0	5.0	-0.9	42	
M50J	6	1.88	4.12	475	0.9	5.0	-1.0	62	
M55J	6	1.91	4.02	540	0.8	5.0	-1.1	78	
M60J	3/6	1.93	3.82	588	0.7	4.7	-1.1	75	
IM7	12	1.78	5.76	292	2.0	5.2	-0.64	5.40	Hexcel (USA)
HM63	12	1.83	4.68	455	1.0	4.9	-1.2	1.07	

Table 3 Comparison of properties of common resin for resin matrix composites

Resin type	Unsaturated polyester	Epoxy	Phenolic	Cyanate ester	Bismaleimide	Polyimide
Processability	Good	Good	Fine	Good	Good	Poor
Mechanical properties	Moderate	Good	Moderate	Good	Good	Fine
Density(g/cm ³)	1.1~1.2	1.2~1.3	1.2~1.3	1.1~1.3	1.2~1.3	1.3~1.4
Thermal stability(°C)	<80	<150	<180	<200	<250	>250
Curing shrinkage (%)	4~6	1~3	8~10	<1	2~4	2~4
Moisture absorption	High	High	High	Low	Medium	High
Coefficient of thermal expansion	High	Medium/High	High	Medium	Medium	Medium
Dimension stability	Fine	Good	Good	Good	Good	Good
Toughness	Poor	Fine	Poor	Fine	Moderate	Poor
Cost	Low	Medium	Low	Medium	Medium	High
Common reinforcement	Glass fiber	Glass fiber Carbon fiber Aramid fiber	Glass fiber	Carbon fiber Quartz fiber	Carbon fiber	Carbon fiber Quartz fiber
Application	Non load-bearing structure	Secondary structure-primary structure	Non load-bearing structure	Secondary structure-primary structure	Primary structure	Primary structure

RESULTS

From Table2, we can found that, the elongation at break of carbon fiber decreases with the increase of modulus owing to the decrease of fiber toughness. Meanwhile, the diameter of carbon fiber decreases, and

the absolute value of thermal expansion coefficient increases with the increase of modulus. Therefore, suitable carbon fiber should be chosen to meet the demand of space mirror. At present, common carbon fibers using for the manufacture of CFRP composite space mirror are high modulus fiber, such as M46J, M55J, and even high modulus fiber, such as M60J, M65.

It can be seen in Table 3, due to their high curing shrinkage, poor moisture resistance and poor toughness, the resins such as unsaturated polyester, phenolic, bismaleimide and polyimide are unsuitable for using in the space area. In other words, the resins suitable for using in the space area must have high dimensional stability and curing shrinkage. Therefore, the toughened epoxy and cyanate ester can meet the demand of space applications. Thus, the preferred resin matrix using for the manufacture of composite space mirror is cyanate ester, and the toughened epoxy resin is also used to manufacturing mirror in a few cases.

To study the process of CFRP composite space mirror, we have developed and prepared high toughened epoxy resin and cyanate ester, the resin grades are E603B and C705 respectively. The carbon fiber is domestic high modulus, PAN-based carbon fibers, and the matrix is cyanate ester C705 in this paper. Fig2 shows preparation process of this prepreg.

Fig.2 Preparation process of the prepreg

A sort of domestic high modulus carbon fiber composite plate were cured and measured, and the properties are shown in Table 4. The carbon fiber composite can meet the design requirements for the prototype space mirror. The surface accuracy of composite prototype space mirror meets the preliminary requirements, and the surface RMS value of mirror is within $4\mu\text{m}$. Numerical simulation and experiment analysis in manufacturing composite space mirror are necessary to study, to improve the surface accuracy of space mirror, which is also our next research focus.

Table 4 Properties of a sort of domestic high modulus carbon fiber composite

No.	Properties	No.	Properties
1	0 °Tensile strength (MPa)	1613	13 0 °Bending modulus (GPa)
2	0 °Tensile modulus (GPa)	303	14 90 °Bending strength (MPa)
3	Primary Poisson ratio	0.33	15 90 °Bending modulus (GPa)
4	90 °Tensile strength (MPa)	15.5	16 0 °shear strength (MPa)
5	90 °Tensile modulus (GPa)	5.91	17 Collected volatile condensable materials_(%)
6	0 °Compression strength (MPa)	799	18 Total mass loss (%)

7	0 °Compression modulus (GPa)	333	19	Water vapor regained (%)	0.051
8	0 °Fracture strain (%)	0.25	20	0 ° Average coefficient of linear expansion (RT~100 ×10 ⁻⁶ /°C)	-0.88
9	90 °Compression strength (MPa)	134	21	0 ° Average coefficient of linear expansion RT~200 ×10 ⁻⁶ /°C)	-0.64
10	90 °Compression modulus (GPa)	7.85	22	90 ° Average coefficient of linear expansion (RT~100 ×10 ⁻⁶ /°C)	35.70
11	90 °Fracture strain (%)	1.65	23	90 ° Average coefficient of linear expansion (RT~200 ×10 ⁻⁶ /°C)	39.42
12	0 °Bending strength (MPa)	1043			

CONCLUSION

This work shows that high modulus carbon fiber reinforced cyanate ester resin matrix composites are the preferred manufacturing materials for CFRP composite space mirror. High toughness cyanate ester resin C705 and the domestic high modulus carbon fiber were selected for preparation of prepreg for composite space mirror. The high modulus carbon fiber composite can meet the surface accuracy requirements for the prototype space mirror in our study.

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